

Study of Value Conflict of Students Studying In Senior Secondary School In Relation To Their Gender, Locality, Management and Academic Achievement

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Abstract:

The main objective of the research was to Study the Value Conflict of Senior Secondary school Students in Related to Gender, Locality, Management and Academic Achievement. The study adopted survey design and collected data from 450 senior secondary schools of Badaun district of Uttar Pradesh by using Value Conflict scale developed and standardized by R. L. Bharadwaj. Collected data was computed using independent sample 't' test and One Way ANOVA. The study observed that, there is gender, management, locality and levels of achievement wise difference and variance in the value conflict assumption of student's studying in senior secondary school.

Key Words: Value, Value Conflict and Senior Secondary School

Introduction:

Values play a large role in education and are a part of daily life. The cultivation of values within the student is the aim of education. In actuality, morals are crucial for every individual to live a successful existence in society. Conflict pertaining to value factors will also arise when practicing values. "Whenever two or more incompatible goals, motives, activity or impulses are active at the same time in relation to desirable or pre-social aspects of the wellbeing of the humanity, they can be said to be the value conflict" Bharadwaj, (2001). The moral stance that is commensurate with pro-choice and anti-abortion is known as value conflict. That is the practice of approaching moral questions in a fundamentally different way, in addition to agreeing on substantive moral concerns Kazi and Narayanappa (2016). From this point of view, value conflicts rise commonly in everyone life. At initial stage it will influence on every individual and in the later years everyone will learn to manage the value conflict based on their experiences. So, there is need of seeing value conflict based on the ages. Because of this reason, Conflict over preferences for intrapersonal and interpersonal values begins to arise in late childhood, but because teenagers are more prone to various forms of conflict, it becomes more noticeable in this age group. So, the adolescents student's majorly face problem related to value conflicts related to aspects. In this concern Kaur and Kaur, (2013) rightly stated that "values are those principles which guide human behavior and put meaning to his existence". In this background the study was undertaken to study the value conflict of senior secondary school student's.

Review of Related Literature:

Tiwari, Nautyal, Mehrotra, and Bhatt, (2012) conducted research on "the study of value

conflicts among adolescents of 12th standard students of Dehradun district. The study found that there is no significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on various dimension of value conflict. Conflicts over values, beliefs and expectation rank high on the list in adolescence.

Chaudhary and Nai, (2013) examined a value conflict profile of primary teachers. This study found significance of difference between means obtained of any two groups of primary teachers, on various dimensions of value conflict scale.

Srivastava, (2018) conducted a study on Impact of culture on the development of value conflict in emerging adulthood. The study revealed that A significant difference is found between the students of Germany and India with respect to the values of Evasion vs. Fortitude, Dependence vs. Self-reliance and Selfishness vs. Probity value. Students of both the countries fall towards the positive dimension 'Love' value,

Sharma, (2019) explored a study of value conflict among degree college students in relation to their socioeconomic status. The study found that there exists difference between value-conflict and socio-economics status of rural and urban students.

From the review of related literature and above discussion it is evident that value conflict is significant factor in school education. Study also reported with selected variable. The present study is also extension of research and also intended to explore the value conflict of senior secondary students in the background of their gender, locality, management and levels of achievement.

Statement of Problem:

The main objective of the research was to Study Of Value Conflict of Students Studying in Senior Secondary School in Relation to Their Gender, Locality, Management And Academic Achievement

Objectives of the Study:

- To study whether the male and female students studying senior secondary school differ in their value conflict.
- To study whether the students studying rural and urban senior secondary school differ their value conflict.
- To study whether the students studying government, aided and private senior secondary school differ their value conflict.
- To study whether the low and high academic achievement students studying senior secondary school differ their value conflict.

Hypothesis of the Study:

- There will be no significant difference in value conflict of male and female students studying in senior secondary school.
- There will be significant difference in value conflict of students studying in rural and urban background senior secondary school.
- There will be no significant difference in value conflict of students studying in government, aided and private senior secondary school.
- There will be no significant difference in value conflict of low and academic and high academic achievement students studying in senior secondary school.

Variables of the Study:

Table: Comparison of differences in value conflict of male and female students studying in senior secondary school.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Male	228	76.6096	14.02990	4.467	.000	S
Female	222	82.7072	14.89723			(p < .05)

It is observed from the table-1 that, the obtained p value is less than .05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in value conflict of male and female students studying in senior secondary school at .05 level of significance, $t(448) = 4.467, p < .05$. Further, the mean comparison indicates that, female

Table: Comparison of differences in value conflict of male and female students studying in senior secondary school.

Locality	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Rural	203	85.4286	11.76244	8.298	.000	NS
Urban	247	74.8421	15.28521			(p < .05)

It is observed from the table-2 that, the obtained p value is less than .05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in value conflict of students studying in rural and urban background senior secondary school at .05 level of significance, $t(448) = 8.298, p < .05$. Further, the mean comparison indicates that, the students studying in rural secondary school found to

The study considered gender, management, locality and level of academic achievement as independent variable and value conflict of senior secondary school as dependent variable.

Research Method of the study:

The study adopted survey design to explore the value conflict assumption of students. The study also intended to explore whether gender, management, locality and level of academic achievement wise difference exist in the value conflict of senior secondary school.

Sample of the Study:

For the present study data collected from the students studying in senior secondary school. A total of 450 senior secondary school students studying in Badaun district of Uttar Pradesh were took part in the survey. The data was collected from government, aided and private senior secondary school.

Tools Used in the Study:

Value Conflict scale developed and standardized by R L. Bharadwaj was used in the study.

Statistical Techniques Used in the Study:

In the study based on the objectives and hypothesis, independent sample 't' test and One Way ANOVA were used to compute the data.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Hypothesis-1: There will be no significant differences in value conflict of male and female students studying in senior secondary school.

students found to be higher value conflict assumption compare to male students studying in secondary school.

Hypothesis-2: There will be no significant differences in value conflict of male and female students studying in senior secondary school.

higher value conflict assumption compare to students studying in urban secondary senior secondary school.

Hypothesis-3: There will be no significant differences in value conflict of students studying in government, aided and private senior secondary school

Table-3: Indicates sum of squares, df, mean square, f-value and p-value for differences in value conflict of students studying in government, aided and private in senior secondary school

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7208.178	2	3604.089	17.762	.000
Within Groups	90702.080	447	202.913		
Total	97910.258	449			

It is observed from the table-2 that, the obtained p value is less than .05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in value conflict of students studying in government, aided and private senior secondary

school at .05 level of significance, $F(2, 447) = 17.762$; $p < .05$. Further, to find out the difference in the mean scores, multiple comparisons are performed using the Tukey post hoc test procedure and reported in the table.

Table-4: Comparison of differences in differences in value conflict of students studying in government, aided and private in senior secondary school

Management	N	Mean	SD	Management	
				Aided	Private
Government	148	83.5878	16.81671	.305 ($p > .05$)	.000 ($p < .05$)
Aided	152	81.1645	15.28729		.000 ($p > .05$)
Unaided	150	74.1333	9.63820		

It is observed from the table-4 that, the obtained p value ($p > .05$) for mean scores of value conflict scores of students studying in government and aided secondary school is higher than .05 level of significance, p value ($p < .05$) for mean scores of value conflict scores of students studying in government and unaided secondary school is less than .05 level of significance and p value ($p < .05$) for mean scores of value conflict scores of students studying in aided and unaided secondary school is less than .05 level of significance. Therefore, there

is significance difference in the value conflict scores of students studying in government and aided secondary school and aided and unaided senior secondary school. Whereas no difference in the mean scores of vale conflict of students studying in government and aided secondary school.

Hypothesis-4: There will be no significant differences in value conflict of low and high academic achievement students studying in senior secondary school.

Table-5: Comparison of differences in value conflict of low and high academic achievement students studying in senior secondary school.

Levels of Academic Achievement	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Low	235	81.5787	14.50454	2.971	.003	S ($p < .05$)
High	215	77.4744	14.78658			

It is observed from the table-4 that, the obtained p value is less than .05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in value conflict of low and academic and high academic achievement students studying in senior secondary school at .05 level of significance, $F(448) = 2.971$; $p < .05$. Further, the mean comparison indicates that, the students of low academic achievement found to be higher value conflict assumption compare to the students of high academic achievement students in senior secondary school.

Major Findings of the Study:

- There is significant difference in value conflict of male and female students studying in senior secondary school at .05 level of significance, $t(448) = 4.467$, $p < .05$.
- There is significant difference in value conflict of students studying in rural and urban background senior secondary school at .05 level of significance, $t(448) = 8.298$, $p < .05$.

- There is significant difference in value conflict of students studying in government, aided and private senior secondary school at .05 level of significance, $F(2, 447) = 17.762$; $p < .05$.
- There is significant difference in value conflict of low and academic and high academic achievement students studying in senior secondary school at .05 level of significance, $F(448) = 2.971$; $p < .05$.

Conclusion:

The findings of the study clearly revealed variance in the value conflict assumption of students studying senior secondary school. The variance indicate that female students showed higher value conflict assumption compare to male students, students studying in rural secondary school showed higher value conflict assumption compare to students studying in urban senior secondary school; students studying government and aided senior secondary school showed higher value conflict assumption compare to students studying in private senior secondary school; and students having low

academic achievement showed higher level of academic achievement compare to high academic achievement. Thus, study found a significant effect of gender, management, locality and level of academic achievement on value conflict assumption of secondary school.

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